

Speculation on Kaniadakis Distribution and Fluctuations

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In (1), it is suggested that the Tsallis distribution is associated with fluctuations to nonlinear spatial motion. In particular, the authors use a “RG (Renormalization Group) point map $f^*(x)$ associated with the intermittency route to chaos” (1).

Specifically, they use $f(x) = x + u \text{abs}(x) \text{ power } z + \dots$ and $f^*(x) = g f^*(f^*(x)/q)$ and obtain a solution for $f^*(x)$ which utilizes the Tsallis $\exp_k(x)$. The Landau Ginzburg equation is also used.

Here we suggest thinking of the Kaniadakis distribution in terms of a fluctuation, but in the context of maximization of entropy MaxEnt. In the Tsallis and Maxwell-Boltzmann maximization of entropy (MaxEnt) approaches there are two constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$. There is no notion of a fluctuation in these a priori constraints. If one wishes to introduce a fluctuation there are two problems. First, it is not clear what the form the fluctuation should be in and secondly, the a priori value of the integral of this constraint is unknown.

We suggest that despite these drawbacks, one may still introduce a fluctuation into a MaxEnt process in the following manner. Given a distribution $p(k, e_i) = f(e_i, k) \text{ power } 1/k$, where k is a parameter such that the probability goes as $e_i/T \text{ power } 1/k$ for $e_i/T \gg 1$, there should be a value of k for which one retrieves the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, namely $k=0$. This places restrictions on the $p(e_i, k) = f(e_i, k) \text{ power } 1/k$. If $k \rightarrow 0$, one must eliminate the k in $f(e_i, k)$ through a limit to $\exp(-ke_i/T) \text{ power } 1/k$. This suggests a possible $f(e_i, k) = 1 - ke_i/T$ which is the Tsallis choice. For $e_i/T \ll 1$, one should also approach the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

We suggest that one may introduce a fluctuation in the following manner. Usually, in the MaxEnt process one maximizes an entropy function subject to a priori constraints. These are introduced with an unknown Lagrange multiplier and usually an integral for each constraint together with its value, e.g. $\int p dp \exp(-pp/2mT) pp/2m = E_{ave}$ and $\int p dp \exp(-pp/2mT) = 1$. Here one knows neither the form of the fluctuation or its integrated a priori value. To bypass this problem, one may assume that one knows instead the value of the Lagrange multiplier. One may impose a value on the Lagrange multiplier by noting that for $e_i/T \ll 1$, the distribution should approach an MB one. Normally, this is described by $1 - e_i/T$ for $e_i/T \ll 1$, but the next term is $.5 e_i^2/T^2$. We suggest that the fluctuation constraint for $e_i/T \ll 1$ (or $k \rightarrow 0$) should to leading order yield $.5 e_i^2/T^2$. This then leads to a function of $1 - k e_i/T + .5 k k e_i^2/T^2 + \dots$ in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit, but in the general case, one has a more complicated fluctuation. One may find the solution $f(xk) \text{ power } 1/k$ ($x = -e_i/T$) which has the proper limits, i.e. $f(kx) = (\sqrt{1+kx} + kx)$ by trial and error. Given this form, one find $F(p) = 1/2k (p \text{ power } k - p \text{ power } -k)$ and $d/dp (p F(p)) = x + .5 (p \text{ power } k + p \text{ power } -k)$. Using the solution for $p(x)$ in the second term, one may find a fluctuation form and multiply it by $p(x)$ to obtain the required constraint. One then has three constraints a $p(e_i)$ ($a = \text{Lagrange multiplier}$), $-1/T p(e_i)$ and $.5 (\sqrt{1+kx} + kx + 1/(\sqrt{1+kx} + kx))$ and can use MaxEnt to find $p(e_i)$ with the third constraint representing fluctuations.

Motivation

The motivation for considering that the Kaniadakis distribution is linked with fluctuations comes from (1). The authors of (1) use a “RG (Renormalization Group) point map $f^*(x)$ associated with the intermittency route to chaos” (1), but apply it to the Tsallis distribution. Specifically, they use $f(x) = x + u \text{abs}(x) \text{ power } z + \dots$ and $f^*(x) = g f^*(f^*(x/q))$ and obtain a solution for $f^*(x)$ which utilizes the Tsallis $\exp_k(x)$. The Landau Ginzburg equation is also used. In other words, they link the Tsallis distribution to fluctuations.

We wish to link the Kaniadakis distribution to fluctuations. Our approach is so different from theirs in that we focus solely on MaxEnt that we refer the reader to (1) for its details. The point we make is that the notion of a fluctuation of the form $x \text{ power } z$ away from a linear x term is introduced in (1) and we think that a Kaniadakis distribution may also be thought of in terms of fluctuations. We suggest that this notion of a fluctuation seems very useful in trying to understand MaxEnt and the Kaniadakis distribution.

Kaniadakis Distribution and the Notion of a Fluctuation

Using the standard Kaniadakis form:

$$F(p) = 1/2k (p(x) \text{ power } k - p(x) \text{ power } -k) \quad \text{where } x = -e_i/T \quad ((1))$$

leads to

$$d/dp (p F(p)) \text{ not} = -e_i/T + \text{constant} \quad ((2))$$

On the RHS of ((2)) we use the usual two constraints

$$\text{Sum over } i p(e_i) = 1 \text{ and Sum over } i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}} \quad ((3))$$

These constraints do not include any kind of a priori fluctuation. The problem is that one cannot use the usual Kaniadakis $F(p)$ ((1)) in a MaxEnt approach using the RHs of ((2)). One has a remaining term equal to:

$$.5 (p(x) \text{ power } k + p(x) \text{ power } -k) \quad ((4))$$

We suggest, however, that such a form may be linked with a fluctuation constraint if one uses the solution

$$p(x) = (\sqrt{1+kx} + kx) \text{ power } 1/k \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{i.e. constraint} = p(x) \{ \sqrt{1+kx} + kx + 1/(\sqrt{1+kx} + kx) \} \quad ((6))$$

The problem is that one would never guess such a constraint a priori and furthermore does not know its integrated value. As a result, it does not seem clear how it could appear in a MaxEnt

problem. To find a way to bypass these two problems, we consider limits of the Kaniadakis case in more detail.

Kaniadakis Distribution and Limiting Cases

The Kaniadakis distribution is based on the probability distribution:

$$f(e_i, k) \text{ power } 1/k \quad ((7))$$

In the limit of $k \rightarrow 0$, one should retrieve the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution. This suggests that:

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow 0} f(e_i, k) \rightarrow \exp(-e_i k/T) \text{ power } 1/k \quad ((8))$$

This in turn gives information about $f(e_i, k)$. It seems that in the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit, one should have $f(e_i, k)$ mimic a power series of $\exp(-k e_i / T)$. This also applies to the $e_i/T \ll 0$ limit because k and e_i/T are multiplied together and only one needs to be small in order for the Maxwell-Boltzmann low e_i/T form to appear.

Imagine that one wishes to have a distribution which includes the consequences of a fluctuation, but does not know the form of the fluctuation or its integrated value (for a constraint). One may simply argue (we suggest) that in the $k \rightarrow 0$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit, that this $f(e_i, k)$ approaches:

$$1 - k e_i/T + .5 k k e_i e_i / T T \quad ((9))$$

It is not enough to have $1 - k e_i/T$ as in the Tsallis case which only includes the constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ as there is no fluctuation. The fluctuation terms must yield $.5 k k e_i e_i / T T$ to leading order in e_i/T which, in this limit, no longer looks like a fluctuation term, but only an extra term in the $\exp(-k e_i/T)$ expansion. A key feature of this approach is that one then knows the factor $.5$ from ((9)) which matches the value of a Lagrange multiplier meaning that one does not need to know the a priori value of the integrated value of the fluctuation.

The problem now becomes finding an $f(kx)$ ($x = -e_i/T$) such that it becomes ((9)) in the $k \rightarrow 0$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit and e_i/T in the $e_i/T \gg 1$ limit.

A simple solution which matches these two criteria is given by:

$$\sqrt{1 + k k x x} + k x = f(kx) \quad ((10))$$

Given the simple form of ((10)), it could be obtained quickly by trial and error. This immediately gives the form of $p(kx)$:

$$p(kx) = (\sqrt{1 + k k x x} + k x) \text{ power } 1/k \quad ((11))$$

If one postulates that entropy density is:

$p F(p)$ with $F(p) = x$, then $F(p) = 1/2k (p^k - p^{-k})$ ((12))

The question is: What is the fluctuation constraint? For MaxEnt, one takes:

$d/dp (p F(p))$ and sets it equal to d/dp (constraint statements multiplied by Lagrange multiplier) ((13))

The usual MB or Tsallis constraints are

$p(e_i)$ and $e_i p(e_i)$ ((13))

The Lagrange multiplier of $e_i p(e_i)$ is taken to be $-1/T$. Clearly these two are not enough for $d/dp (p F(p))$ using ((12))

In particular:

$$\begin{aligned} d/dp (p F(p)) &= 1/2k ((1+k) p^k - (1-k) p^{-k}) \\ &= 1/2k (p^k - p^{-k}) + 1/2 (p^k + p^{-k}) \end{aligned} \quad ((14))$$

The first term in ((14)) is x , so the second is linked with a fluctuation of the following form. One first uses ((11)) to convert the second term in ((14)) into the x variable and then multiplies it by $p(x)$. (For example, a constraint on $e_i e_i p(e_i)$ would take the form $\sum_i e_i e_i p(e_i) = \text{a priori number}$.)

This leads to the fluctuation constraint:

$$p(e_i) \cdot \left(\sqrt{1+kx} + kx + 1 / (\sqrt{1+kx} + kx) \right) \quad ((15))$$

with ((15)) and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = \text{Eave}$, one may introduce a MaxEnt with fluctuations whose solution is:

$$p(e_i) = \left(\sqrt{1+kx} + kx \right)^{1/k} \quad ((16))$$

As a result, we suggest that the Kaniadakis distribution may be considered as a fluctuation based one with a rather complicated fluctuation constraint ((15)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, for the Tsallis and Maxwell-Boltzmann maximization of entropy (MaxEnt) approaches, one uses the straightforward non-fluctuation constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = \text{Eave}$. We ask: What happens if there are fluctuations? The idea of fluctuations is introduced in (1) using the renormalization group and Landau-Ginzburg equation and applied to the Tsallis case. We do not wish to follow that approach here, but do consider a

priori fluctuations in a statistical system in addition to the two usual constraints. The problem is that one has no idea what form this fluctuation takes, nor its integrated a priori value.

We suggest that one may bypass this problem in the following way. We note that for either $k \rightarrow 0$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$, $p(x_k) = f(x_k)$ power $1/k$ where $x = -e_i/T$ means that for $k \rightarrow 0$ one must obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Usually, in this limit one would write $1+x_k$ as in the Tsallis case. If, however, one has a fluctuation in the system, its expansion should bring in a possible x_k^2 term with some coefficient. We suggest that this coefficient must be $.5$ so that one has $.5 k x_k^2$, the second order term in an $\exp(-kx)$ expansion. Knowing $.5$ is like knowing the value of the Lagrange multiplier, we argue.

One may now seek a function: $f(x_k)$ power $1/k$ such that it behaves as x_k power $1/k$ for $e_i/T \gg 1$ and as $(1+kx+.5 kx^2)$ power $1/k$ for $e_i/T \ll 1$. A simple solution is: $p(kx) = (\sqrt{1+kx^2} + kx)$ power $1/k$. This leads to: $F(p) = x = 1/2k (p \text{ power } k - p \text{ power } -k)$ and entropy density as: $p(x) F(p)$.

One may finally ask: What fluctuation constraint would lead to such a result? The two usual constraints are $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = E_{ave}$. Using $d/dp (pF(p)) = 1/2k (x \text{ power } k - p \text{ power } -k) + .5 (p \text{ power } k + p \text{ power } -k)$, one may convert the second term to the $e_i/T = v$ variable and then multiply it by $p(x)$ to obtain the MaxEnt fluctuation constraint: $p(e_i) \{ \sqrt{1+kx^2} + kx + 1/(\sqrt{1+kx^2} + kx) \}$ where $x = -e_i/T$.

References

1. Robledo A, Velarde C. How, Why and When Tsallis Statistical Mechanics Provides Precise Descriptions of Natural Phenomena. *Entropy (Basel)*. 2022 Dec 1;24(12):1761. doi: 10.3390/e24121761. PMID: 36554166; PMCID: PMC9777765. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9777765/>